

AN ANATOMICAL REVIEW OF THE CONCEPT OF ‘SNAYU’

Dr. Priyanka Upadhyay¹, Dr. Sushil Dwivedi², Dr. Sachin Dwivedi³

1 Assistant Professor of Rachana Sharir Department, Raigarh Medical College & Hospital of Ayurveda, Raigarh (C.G.)

2 Associate Professor of Rachana Sharir Department, Shri N.P.A. Govt. Ayurvedic Medical College, Raipur(C.G.)

3 Assistant Professor of Kriya Sharir Department, Raigarh Medical College & Hospital of Ayurveda, Raigarh (C.G.)

Abstract- In *Rachana sharir* of *Ayurveda* many of the structures are unclear to us since they have a physiological basis. The idea of correlation was developed to comprehend these systems, and it sparked numerous controversies. In several *Ayurvedic Samhita* 's *Sharir Sthan* explained about *Sira, Snayu, Peshi, Dhamani, Asthi & Sandhi* etc and also explains their significance as well as various clinical situations. *Snayu* is one of important structure in human body. There is controversy on the concept of *Snayu*. The majority of academics classify *Snayu* as ligament, muscle, tendon, nerve etc. The *Snayu* is a crucial component of the body. It is mentioned several times in the *Ayurvedic* literature including *Snayu Marma, Agnikarma, Shastra Karma, Bandh Karma, Snayugat vatvyadhi, Sivan Karma* and *Siravedha*. Therefore, for a scholar to comprehend the concept of *Snayu*, they must first understand what *Snayu* genuinely means. A literature review was conducted for this aim. The statement made by *Maharshi Shushrut* that *Sandhibandhan* is *Snayu*'s primary purpose could be cause.

Keywords – *Snayu, Kandara, Peshi*, ligament, Tendon, Aponeurosis, fascia, joint.

Introduction – In *Ayurveda* literature *Rachana Sharir* is basic and fundamental subject. It deals with the structure of human body. *Sharir Sthan* mention in *Shushrut Samhita* is considered as *Shrestha* among all the *Sharir Sthan* explain in *Samhitas*. In *Shushrut Samhita* *Maharshi Shushruta* has one by one defined the anatomical topics like *Srotas, Sira, Dhamni, Marma, Kandara, Snayu* etc in *Sharir Sthan*. *Snayu* is one of important structure in human body. Literally the term *Snayu* means to bind. It is explained as a structure which helps in binding the joints and helps the movements of joints. It refers to a band of fibres and helps to retain body posture via imparting weight carrying capacity.^[1]

Most of the structural entities explained in our *Samhita* are very difficult to understand. It is very important to interpret the anatomical terms with reference to the *Samhita*. There is a lacuna in this interpretation. *Snayu Sharir* is one of such area which needs much more research. The present study we will try to fulfil the lacunae regarding *Snayu*.

Historical Review of *Snayu*-

Atharvaveda- According to *Atharvaveda* the word *Snayu* is mentioned as body part and also described location of *Snayu Samsthan* (below the *Mamsha*).^[2]

Naradprivajkopnishad – According to this *Upnishad Snayu* is one of body part.^[3]

Agnipurana – According to *Agnipurana* the word *Snayu* is mentioned as *Pitraj Bhav*. The number of *Snayu* are 900.^[4]

Ayurvedic review of Snayu- In this study *Snayu* will explain in following manner.

Vyutpatti – The word *Snayu* is formed from the word root (*Dhatu*) ‘*Sna*’. ‘*Sna*’ *Dhatu* when combined with ‘*un*’ and ‘*yuk*’ *pratyaya* from the word *Snayu*.^[5]

Nirukti- According to *Vachaspathyam* ‘*Snayu*’ is a *Strilinga Shabda*. Its function is binding the body.^[6]

Synonyms – *Kandra, Peshi, Nasha, Dhanush ki Dori*.^[7]

A tendon, a muscle described as a tubular vessel attached to the bones at either end and carrying vital air.^[8]

Utpatti of Snayu- According to *Charaka Samhita* ‘*Snayu*’ are derived from *Meda Dhatu*.^[9]

According to *Sushrut Samhita* from the unctuous portion of *Medas* both *Sira* and *Snayu* are formed, *Sira* arise from mild cooking (*Mridu Paak*) and *Snayu* from hard cooking (*Khar Paak*).^[10]

According to *Astanga Samgraha* the essence of *Meda* is the *Asthi, Snayu* and *Sandhi*.^[11]

Definition of Snayu – *Snayu* are said to bind *Mamsha, Asthi, Medas and Sandhiya* (joints). They are firmer than *Sira*(vein).^[12]

Snayu is a subsidiary tissue looking like hemp by which bow- strings are made.^[13]

In *Ayurveda literatures* ‘*Snayu*’ is mentioned as *Pitraj Bhav*.^[14]

Maharshi Shushruta included *Snayu* one of *Pratyanga*.^[15]

Types of Snayu and their position - According to *Maharshi Shushruta* ‘*Snayu*’ are four types.^[16]

- *Pratanvatya Snayu* – *Pratanvatya Snayu* are presents in *Sakha* (extremities) and *Sarva Sandhi* (all bony joints).
- *Vritta Snayu* – *Vritta Snayu* are known as *Kandara* (Tendons) by experts.
- *Sushira Snayu* – *Sushira Snayu* are present at the end of *Amasaya* (stomach), *Pakvashaya* (large intestine) and *Basti* (urinary bladder).
- *Prithula Snayu* – *Prithula Snayu* are present in *Parsva* (flanks), *Uras* (chest), *Pristha* (back) and *Sira* (Head).

Numbers of Snayu – According to *Agnipurana, Charak Samhita, Shushrut Samhita* and *Astanga Samgraha* total numbers of *Snayu* are 900 in human body.^{[17][18][19][20]}

According to *Maharshi Shushruta* the further classification of 900 *Snayu* are mentioned in following manner^[21] :-

1) In *Urdhva & Adho Shakha* (upper & lower extremities)- total 600 *Snayu* are found (150 *Snayu* in each extremity).

A. in one finger -6 *Snayu* (hence all fingers 30 *Snayu*)

B. Foot along with ankle – 30 *Snayu*

C. leg – 30 *Snayu*

D. Knee- 10 *Snayu*

E. Thigh – 40 *Snayu*

F. Hip – 10 *Snayu*

2) In *Kostha* (Trunk)- 230 *Snayu*

3) In *Urdhvagriva* (Head & neck)- 70 *Snayu*

So total 900 *Snayu* are found in human body.

Location of *Snayu*:-According to *Acharya Charak* the joints of bones are called bony joints. The *Snayu* and *Kandra* tied in these joints. This is the middle path of the disease.^[22] According to *Maharshi Shushrut* all types of *Peshi* cover the *Sandhi*, *Asthi*, *Sira* and *Snayu*.^[23] According to *Acharya Kashyap* in the body, the bones are tied with *Snayu* and *Snayu* are covers with *Mamsha* (flesh) which are continuously nourished by *Siras* whereas, skin covers the exterior.^[24] According to *Acharya indu* commenter of *Astanga Samgraha* the *Peshi* themselves are further converted into *Snayu* which become fleshy.^[25]

Function of *Snayu* :-1) Binding agent- According to *Maharshi Shushrut* the human body can support weight as long as the joints are securely fastened by *Snayu*, just as a boat made of side by side wooden planks that is directed by a man known as the 'boatman'. Similarly, the human body will be able to carry weight, so long as the joints are fastened tightly by *Snayu* in many ways.^[26]

According to *Bhav Prakash* *Snayu* bind the *Mamsha*, *Asthi* and *Medas* patently and as these are stronger than *Siras* can bind the joints also very strongly.^[27]

2) Movements of joints- According to *Maharshi Shushrut* if *Snayu* is injured it causes following symptoms, shortening, debility of body parts, inability to perform their action etc.^[28] This symptoms clearly indicates towards the involvements of movements of joints.

Discussion – References of *Snayu*, from *Ayurvedic* literatures has been complied and correlated of these references with modern anatomy was done, Considering and correlating the references regarding the *Snayu* it has been stated that:

In the context of synonyms of *Snayu*, *Kandara*, *Peshi* & bow strings like structures which binds the *Sandhi* (joints) known as *Snayu*. Hence, we can consider ligaments and tendons both under '*Snayu*'. According to *Astanga Samgraha* *Kandra* is *Maha Snayu*.^[29] According to *Bhav Prakash*^[30], *Dalhan commentary*^[31], *Vrihchhariram Kandara* is *Maha Snayu*.^[32] So we can consider all tendons under the structures of *Snayu*.

In the context of definitions of *Snayu*; *Snayu* binds *Mamsha*, *Asthi*, *Meda* and *Sandhi*. So we can say that all tendons, ligaments, fascia and aponeurosis under the *Ayurvedic* terminology *Snayu*. Ligaments are similar to tendons or fasciae as they are all made of connective tissue. The differences in them are in the connections that they make; ligaments connect one bone to

other bone, tendons connect muscle to bone and fascia bind or enclose muscle to other muscle, they all are related in the musculoskeletal system of the human body.

Ligaments- A ligament is a cord or band of connective tissue uniting two structures. Commonly found in association with joint, ligaments are of two types. Most are composed of dense bundles of collagen fibres and are unstretchable under normal conditions (e.g. the iliofemoral ligament of the hip joint and the collateral ligaments of the elbow joint). The second type is composed largely of elastic tissue and can therefore regain its original length after stretching (e.g. the ligamentum flavum of the vertebral column and the calcaneonavicular ligament of the foot).^[33]

Tendon- The fleshy part of the muscles is referred to as its belly. The ends of a muscle are attached to bones, cartilage or ligaments by cords of fibrous tissue called tendons.^[34]

Aponeurosis- Occasionally, flattened muscles are attached by a thin but strong sheet of fibrous tissue called an aponeurosis.^[35]

On the basis of anatomy & physiology of *Snayu* we can consider following structures under 4 types of *Snayu* with their positions: -1)*Pratanvati Snayu* – which presents all *Sakha & Sandhi*. The function of *Snayu* is to bind, hence we can say that all tendons & ligaments under *Pratanvati Snayu*. E.g. Ligamentum Patellae etc.

2)*Vritta Snayu* – which are known as *Kandara*; hence we can say that all tendons and cords under *Vrutta Snayu*. E.g. Tendon of flexor digitorum superficialis muscle etc

3)*Sushir Snayu*- which are presents at the ends of *Amashaya*, *Pakvasaya* and *Basti*. Hence we can say that sphincter muscles, hiatus for urethra, visceral ligaments, anorectal hiatus under *Shushir Snayu*. E.g. Pyloric sphincter etc.

4)*Prithu Snayu*- which are present in *Parsva*(flanks), *Uras* (chest), *Pristha* (back) and *Sira*(head), hence we can say that deep fascia and aponeurosis under *Pruthu Snayu*.

E.g. Aponeurosis of external oblique muscle etc.

Forces applied on skeletal muscles are transferred to bone through tendons, aponeuroses and fasciae, whereas ligaments prevent excessive separation of adjacent bones, because all of these structures comprise dense fibrous connective tissues containing a high proportion of type I collagen.^[36]

In the end we can say *Snayu* is a fibrous tissue containing structure in the body. Hence we can say that all fibrous tissue containing structures like ligaments, tendons, aponeurosis and fascia under the structure of *Snayu*

In the context of location of *Snayu* according to *Acharya Charak* the bony joints are tied with *Snayu* and *Kandra*. According to *Maharshi Shushrut* all types of *Peshi* cover the *Snayu*. According to *Acharya Kashyap* the bones are tied with *Snayu* & *Snayu* are covered with *Mamsha*. According to *Acharya Indu* the *Peshi* themselves are further converted into *Snayu* become fleshy. Hence it can be stated that *Snayu* is situated below the *Peshi* (end of the *Peshi*) and binds the all joints. So we can correlate all tendons and ligaments with *Snayu* because a ligament is a cord or band of connective tissue uniting two structures. Commonly found in association with joint. The ends of a muscle are attached to bones, cartilage or ligaments by cords of fibrous tissue called tendons.

In the context of *Snayu Prayojan* (function of *Snayu*) *Maharshi Shushrut* has mentioned that *Snayu* is like ropes in our body. Like the rope holds the wooden planks together, *Snayu* holds the body together making it capable of weight bearing, So long as the joints are fastened tightly by *Snayu* in many ways. In the end it can be correlate the ligaments and tendons, because ligaments and tendons fixed and support the joints and make a joint weight bearing part of body.

According to *Maharshi Shushrut* if *Snayu* is injured the person is unable to perform action like contraction, relaxation etc. These symptoms clearly indicate towards the involvements of movements of joints.

Conclusion- *Snayu* is a structural entity which is binding *Mamsha, Asthi, Medas & Sandhi*. *Snayu* is used as bow string owing to its strength. An overall observation and discussion of these structure gives a conclusion that *Snayu* is a fibrous tissue containing structure in the body. Hence we can interpret all fibrous connecting structures like ligaments, tendons, aponeurosis and fascia under the structure of *Snayu*. The meaning of *Snayu* varies depending on context , when referring to ligaments that link bones and joints ,when referring to tendons & fascia that binds muscles and when referring to aponeurosis that binds the *Meda* (adipose tissue). There are four different types of *Snayu* which we can refer to as the object below:-

- Ligaments & tendons are *Pratanvati Snayu*.
- Tendons & cords are *Vrutta Snayu*.
- Aponeurosis and fascia are *Pruthu Snayu*.
- Sphincters and ligaments of the viscera are *Sushir Snayu*.

Snayu is one of very important fibrous tissue containing structure in human body which binds joint together makes them efficient to bear the weight of whole body and helps the joints movement. *Snayu* is very strong, hard structure due to *Sthir guna* of *Pitraj Bhav* Hence it can be stated that *Snayu* carries out the function of holding, covering and providing strength, support & movement to all joints of human body.

References:-

1. Shushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2017 S. Sharir sthan chapter 5/41-42. page no. 169.
2. Atharvaveda Samhita, part 2, Vedmurti Pandit Shri Ram sharma Acharya, Shanti kunj , Haridwar (u.p.) 2002, Kand 12 page no. 41.
3. 108 Upnishad, Naradprivajkopnishad updesha 3, Vedmurti Pandit Shri Ram sharma Acharya, gaytri tapobhumi, Mathura (u.p) 2005, Mantra 40/48, page no. 133.
4. Agnipuran Ki Aayurvediya Anusandhanatmak Samiksha, Dr. Vivekanand Pandey, Shri Satguru Pablication Delhi, 1997, page no. 50.
5. Shabd kalpadrum, 5th part, Shri vardaprashad Vsuna tadanujen Shri Haricharan Vsuna, Choukhambha series office, Varanasi, 2002, page no. 1456.
6. Vachaspatyam , 6th part, Shri Taranathkrvachspati Bhattacharyen, Choukhambha Sanskrit series office, Varanasi, 2002, page no. 5394.
7. Sanskrit-Sabdarth-Koustumbh, Swar. Chaturvedi Dwarkaprashad Sharma, M.R.A.S And Pandit Tarinish jha, Ramnarayan lal beni Prasad Prakashak, Ilahabad (u.p), 1971, page no 1303.
8. Shabd Sagar, Jivananda vidyasagara Bhattacharya, Mukerjee & Company 1900 page no 814

9. Charak Samhita vidyutani 2nd part, Chukhambha Bharti Acadamy, Varanashi 2018, Chikitsa Sthan 15/17, page no.
10. Sushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2017 Sharir Sthan chapter 4/27-29, page no. 117.
11. Astanga Samgraha, vol 2, Prof. K.R Srikantha murthy, Choukhambha Orientalia Varanasi, 2005, Sharir Sthan Chapter 6/29, page no. 85.
12. Sharangdhar Samhita, Acharya Sharangadhar, Jiwan prada hindi commentary, dr.smt.Shailaja Srivastava, Lucknow (U.P.) Chapter 5/36, page no 42.
13. Sushrut Samhita Commentry, Nibandhasangraha Commentry, Shri Dalhanacharya, Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Choukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, (u.p.), 2014 Shutra Sthan 25/20-21, page no. 119
14. Sushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2019 Sharir Sthan chapter 3/43, page no. 101.
15. Sushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2017 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/5, page no. 148.
16. Sushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2017 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/38-40, page no. 167.
17. Agnipuran Ki Aayurvediya Anusandhanatmak Samiksha, Dr. Vivekanand Pandey, Shri Satguru Pablication Delhi, 1997, page no. 50.
18. Charak Samhita, Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, volume 1st, Chukhambha Bharti Acadamy, Varanashi 2018 Sharir Sthan 7/14, page no. 926.
19. Shushrut Samhita Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2019 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/34, page 167.
20. Astanga Samgraha, Prof. K.R Srikantha murthy, Choukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, 2016, Sharir Sthan 5/49, page no. 70.
21. Sushrut Samhita, DR Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2019 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/34 -37, page no. 167.
22. Charak Samhita, Dr Brahmanand Tripathi, volume 1, Choukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi 2021. Chapter 11/48, page no. 246.
23. Shushrut Samhita DR. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2019 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/52, page no. 172.
24. Kasyapa Samhita Vrddhajivakiya Tantra, Pandit Hemaraja Sarma, Shri Satyapala Bhisagacharya Choukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi, 2022 Sharir Sthan chapter 4, page no 114.
25. Sasilekha Sanskrit commentary by Indu, Astanga samgraha, prof. Jyotir Mitra, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series office, Varanasi, 2008, page no 306.
26. Shushrut Samhita, Dr. Bhaskargovind Ghanekar, New Delhi-110002, 2017 Sharir Sthan chapter 5/41-42, page no 169.
27. Bhav Prakash, Shri Brahms Shankar Mishra, Pratham Bhag, Varanashi, 2002, Choukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, chapter 3/162, page no. 162.
28. Shushrut Samhit, Ambikadutta Shastri, Choukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanashi 2007, chapter 25/37, page no. 106.
29. Astanga Samgraha, Kaviraj Atridevgupt, Krishnadas Acadmi, Varanashi, 2002, Sharir Sthan Chapter 5/52, page no. 71.
30. Bhav Prakash, Shri Brahms Shankar Mishra, Pratham Bhag, Varanashi, 2002, Choukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan chapter 3/267, page no. 80

- 31.**Sushrut Samhita Commentry, Nibandhasangraha Commentry, Shri Dalhanacharya, Vaidya Jadavji Trikamji Acharya, Choukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi,(u.p.),2014 Sharir Sthan 5/29, page no.367-368.
- 32.**Brihchchariram, Vaidyaratna P.S. Variyar, Choukhambha Sanskrit Series office, Varanashi,2005 chaper 5 page no 25.
- 33.**Clinical Anatomy by regions, Richard S. Snell, Edition 8, New Delhi, 2010,page no. 17.
- 34.**Clinical Anatomy by regions , Richard S.Snell, Edition 8,New Delhi, 2010, page no .8
- 35.**Clinical Anatomy by regions, Richard S. Snell, Edition 8. New Delhi, 2010,page no 8.
- 36.**Gray's anatomy, Henry gray, lippicotwilliams, 4th edition .Publishers Elsevier IE (Short Disc) Elsevier Health, 2019, page no 118.